

Orchestrating complex application architectures in heterogeneous clouds: the INDIGO-DataCloud case

Álvaro López García · Pablo Orviz
Fernández · Miguel Caballer · Germán
Moltó · Sahdev Zala · Mathieu Velten

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Abstract Cloud infrastructures are now widely adopted across technology industries and research institutions. However, single cloud providers may not fully satisfy more complex user requirements, and to cope with them, a solution that do not rely on a single cloud environment but instead allow resource provisioning from external providers is required. As a result, in the recent years there has been a growing interest in developing hybrid cloud solutions that bind together distinct and heterogeneous cloud infrastructures. In this paper we will describe the orchestration approach for heterogeneous clouds being implemented within the INDIGO-DataCloud project, based on the OASIS Topology and Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) standard.

Keywords Cloud-Computing · Heterogeneous-Cloud · Multi-Cloud · Open-Source · TOSCA

1 Introduction

INDIGO-DataCloud is an European Union's Horizon 2020 funded project that aims at developing a data and computing platform targeting scientific communities, deployable on multiple hardware and provisioned over hybrid (private

A. López García · P. Orviz Fernández
Instituto de Física de Cantabria.
Centro Mixto CSIC - UC. Santander, Spain.
E-mail: aloga@ifca.unican.es

Miguel Caballer · Germán Moltó
Instituto de Instrumentación para Imagen Molecular (I3M).
Centro Mixto CSIC - Universitat Politècnica de València - CIEMAT. Valencia, Spain.

Sahdev Zala
IBM Raleigh. North Carolina. USA.

Mathieu Velten
European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)

or public) e-infrastructures. By filling existing gaps in the three-layer cloud computing model i.e. IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service) and SaaS (Software as a Service), INDIGO-DataCloud is helping application developers, resources providers, e-infrastructures and scientific communities to overcome current challenges in the cloud computing, storage and network areas.

The project's design specification has put the focus not only in evolving available open-source cloud components, but also in developing new solutions to cope with the project targets, introducing as a result innovative advancements at the layer of IaaS, e.g. container support for the adopted platforms, at the layer of PaaS, e.g. by creating SLA-based orchestration components that support deployments on multi-Clouds and, finally, at the layer of SaaS, e.g. by developing high-level REST and graphical user interfaces to facilitate the usage of computing infrastructures for different scientific communities.

The heterogeneity in the IaaS platforms has been addressed by the adoption of the two leading open-source Cloud Management Platforms (CMP), *OpenStack* and *OpenNebula*. *OpenStack* is a major open-source collaboration that develops a cloud operating system that controls large pools of compute, storage, and networking resources throughout a datacenter, all managed through a dashboard that gives administrators control while empowering their users to provision resources through a web interface. *OpenNebula* provides a simple but feature-rich and flexible solution for the comprehensive management of virtualized data centers to enable private, public and hybrid IaaS clouds. *OpenNebula* interoperability leverages existing IT assets and avoids vendor lock-in. It is an enterprise-ready solution that includes the functionality needed to provide an on-premises (private) cloud offering, and to offer public cloud services. The disparity in the maturity level of the key components needed by INDIGO-DataCloud project have brought along multiple developments in both CMPs codebase, in many cases resulting in upstream contributions¹².

The interoperability required to orchestrate resources either in *OpenStack* or *OpenNebula* CMPs from the PaaS layer has been provided by the usage of the TOSCA (Topology and Specification for Cloud Applications) [10] open standard. The INDIGO-DataCloud project considered this standard as it is currently enabling a unique interoperable Cloud ecosystem supported by a large and growing number of international industry leaders. TOSCA is a Domain Specific Language (DSL) to define interoperable descriptions of cloud applications, services, platforms, data and infrastructure along with their requirements, capabilities, relationship and policies. TOSCA enables portability and automated management across multiple clouds regardless of the underlying platform or infrastructure.

As a result of adopting TOSCA, three additional open software components are taking part on the orchestration solution in the INDIGO-DataCloud project: *TOSCA Parser* is an OpenStack open-source tool to parse documents

¹ <http://stackalytics.com/?release=all&metric=commits&module=tosca-parser>

² <http://stackalytics.com/?release=all&metric=commits&module=heat-translator>

expressed using the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML [16]. *Heat Translator* translates non-Heat templates (e.g. TOSCA templates) to native OpenStack's orchestration language HOT (Heat Orchestration Template). Last but not least, the *Infrastructure Manager* (IM) [5] is a TOSCA compliant orchestrator, which relies on the *TOSCA Parser*, that enables the deployment and configuration of the virtual infrastructures over a large set of different on-premises CMPs (e.g. OpenNebula and OpenStack) and public Cloud providers (e.g. Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform, Microsoft Azure).

2 Background and related work

The usage and promotion of Open Standards in the cloud as a way to obtain more interoperable, distributed and open infrastructures is a topic that has been already discussed [17, 12]. Major actors [9] agree that these principles should drive the evolution of cloud infrastructures (specially scientific clouds) as the key to success over closed infrastructures.

As a matter of fact, the European Commission recommended, back in 2004, the usage of Open Standards in its "European Interoperability Framework for pan-European eGovernment Services" [8]. In the same line, the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has encouraged that US national agencies should specify cloud computing standards in their public procurements [4]. Similarly, the United Kingdom Government provided a set of equivalent principles in 2014 [18].

However, providers and users perceive that lower level (i.e. infrastructure provision and management) standards hinder the adoption of cloud infrastructures. Cloud technologies and frameworks tend to have a fast development pace, adding new functionalities as they evolve, whereas standards' evolution is sometimes not as fast as the underlying technologies. This has been perceived as a negative fact limiting the potential of a given cloud infrastructure, that sees functionality and flexibility decreased. On top of this, infrastructure management is also perceived too lower level when moving to more service-centric approaches that require not only the deployment and management of services, but also all their operational concerns (like fault or error handling, autoscaling, etc) [11].

In this service-centric context, cloud orchestration is being considered more and more important, as it will play the role needed to perform the abstractions needed to deploy complex service architectures. Cloud orchestration involves the automated arrangement, coordination and management of cloud resources (i.e. compute, storage and network) to meet to the user's needs and requirements.

Several open source orchestration tools and services exist in the market, but most of them come with the limitation of being focused to a specific cloud provider or management framework. As an example we can cite OpenStack Heat³ and its YAML-based DSL called Heat Orchestration Template

³ Heat: <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Heat>

(HOT) is native to OpenStack. OpenNebula also provides its own JSON-based multi-tier cloud application orchestration called OneFlow⁴. Cloudify⁵ and Terraform⁶ provide orchestration across different Cloud providers. Cloudify supports TOSCA but is not currently able to deploy on OpenNebula sites. However, Terraform does not provide support to TOSCA. As stated earlier, in INDIGO-DataCloud the Infrastructure Manager (IM)⁷ was selected as the orchestration tool due to its ability to support TOSCA-based deployments and the variety of Cloud back-ends, including the EGI Federated Cloud⁸ a large-scale pan-european federated IaaS Cloud to support scientific research.

2.1 TOSCA

The Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) [10] is an open standard language to model cloud workloads developed by the OASIS [1] nonprofit consortium. It uses the concept of service templates to describe cloud workloads as a topology template, which is a graph of node templates modeling the components a workload is made up of and including relationship templates modeling the relations between those components. TOSCA also provides a type system of node types to describe the possible building blocks for constructing a service template, as well as relationship type to describe possible kinds of relations. Both node and relationship types may define lifecycle operations to implement the behavior an orchestration engine can invoke when instantiating a service template.

The TOSCA standard has been supported by several companies as contributors, reviewers, implementers or users. These companies include, AT&T, Bank of America, Brocade, Cisco, Fujitsu, GigaSpaces, Huawei, IBM, Intel, Red Hat, SAP, VMWare, Vnomic and ZTE corporation. The usage of TOSCA was already made practical by OpenStack projects like TOSCA Parser and Heat Translator. The TOSCA Parser and Heat Translator projects are easy to consume via PyPI packages or directly from the master branch of source code.

2.2 TOSCA Parser

The TOSCA Parser [15] is an OpenStack project, although it is not restricted to an OpenStack environment. The TOSCA Parser is able to read TOSCA templates, TOSCA Cloud Service Archive (CSAR) and TOSCA Simple Profile for Network Functions Virtualization (NFV), creating in-memory graphs of TOSCA nodes and their relationship, as illustrated in Figure 1.

⁴ OneFlow: http://docs.opennebula.org/5.2/advanced_components/application_flow_and_auto-scaling/index.html

⁵ Cloudify: <http://getcloudify.org>

⁶ Terraform: <http://terraform.io>

⁷ IM: <http://www.grycap.upv.es/im>

⁸ EGI FedCloud: <https://www.egi.eu/federation/egi-federated-cloud/>

Fig. 1 The in-memory representation of TOSCA nodes.

2.3 Heat Translator

The OpenStack Heat Translator [14] project enables integration of TOSCA into an OpenStack cloud. With Heat Translator a user can translate TOSCA templates to the OpenStack native HOT language. These templates can then be automatically deployed in an OpenStack cloud (Figure 2).

Fig. 2 Heat Translator Architecture.

The Heat Translator project is well integrated into OpenStack (Figure 3), and it uses various OpenStack projects for translation purposes (like image and instance type mapping) and it is also consumed by other OpenStack official projects like the OpenStack NFV Orchestration project, Tacker [13].

Fig. 3 Heat Translator OpenStack integration.

Listing 1 TOSCA document equivalent to Figure 2.

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0

topology_template:
  node_templates:
    my_server:
      type: tosca.nodes.Compute
      capabilities:
        host:
          properties:
            num_cpus: 2
            disk_size: 10 GB
            mem_size: 512 MB
          os:
            properties:
              architecture: x86_64
              type: linux
              distribution: RHEL
              version: 6.5
```

Listing 2 HOT document equivalent to Listing 1.

```
heat_template_version: 2013-05-23

parameters: {}
resources:
  my_server:
    type: OS::Nova::Server
    properties:
      flavor: m1.medium
      image: rhel-6.5-test-image
      user_data_format: SOFTWARE_CONFIG
outputs: {}
```

Listing 1 shows a TOSCA document that, when passed to the Heat Translator, resulted in the HOT output shown in Listing 2.

2.4 Infrastructure Manager

The Infrastructure Manager (IM) [5] enables to perform the orchestration, deployment and configuration of the virtual infrastructures over a large set of different cloud providers: Cloud Management Platforms such as OpenNebula or OpenStack, public clouds such as Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Platform or Microsoft Azure and also federated clouds such as the EGI Federated Cloud [6] or FogBow [3].

Figure 4 shows the scheme of the IM procedure. It receives the TOSCA template and contacts the cloud site using their own native APIs to orchestrate the deployment and configuration of the virtual infrastructure. The IM also uses the TOSCA parser to parse and load in memory the TOSCA documents received as input. Once the resources have been deployed and they are running, the IM selects one of them as the "master" node and installs and configures Ansible [7] to launch the contextualization agent that will configure all the nodes of the infrastructure. The master node requires a public IP accessible from the IM service and must be connected with the rest of nodes of the infrastructure (either via a public or private IP). Once the node is configured, the IM will launch the contextualization agent to configure all the nodes using the defined Ansible playbooks.

Fig. 4 The Infrastructure Manager (IM).

3 TOSCA orchestration within INDIGO-DataCloud architecture

INDIGO-DataCloud project is providing a solution for deploying cloud applications in multiple CMPs that may need complex topologies and operational requirements, such as auto-scaling resources in and out according to the application needs. Therefore it is a perfect scenario for using TOSCA standard

Fig. 5 Simplified architecture of the usage of TOSCA for the deployment of computing clusters in INDIGO-DataCloud

to orchestrate resources in heterogeneous environments, guiding the operation management throughout the application lifecycle. The tools described in the previous section provide the functionalities needed to cope with the orchestration needs of those cloud applications at the infrastructure and platform level.

Figure 5 describes a simplification of the INDIGO-DataCloud architecture that enables the deployment of complex application layouts. In particular, the figure describes the workflow that involves both the TOSCA-based provision of the computing resources and their dynamic management for an Apache Mesos cluster. As depicted in the figure, two frameworks are deployed on top of the Mesos cluster: Chronos, for the fault-tolerant execution of jobs and Marathon to spawn and monitor long-running services (such as databases, for example).

The deployment of the final user application starts from the TOSCA document that describes the application requirements. In this document, the image that contains the already-deployed application is referenced. The INDIGO-DataCloud solution applies then a different approach based on the presence of the user application image at the target cloud provider. Note that this image

could take the form of a virtual appliance or a Docker container image; either case the procedure to be followed remains invariable since these images must be locally available at the target site.

1. Whenever the requested image is registered at the cloud site, the configuration step is removed, so the user application is spawned right away without the need of any image contextualization.
2. For those cases where the pre-configured image is not at the local catalogue, the deployment of the application is performed on a vanilla virtual machine or Docker container using Ansible roles. Therefore the application deployment is automatically done, without any user intervention. The Ansible role deals with the installation and configuration of a given application, so every application supported in the project need to have its corresponding role online available before its actual instantiation.

An user application made available through this approach will notably take more time to be deployed, when compared with the pre-configured image instantiation described above. But using Ansible roles at this stage allows a more flexible image customization since they support a wide set of platforms and operating system distributions, thus they are not being constrained to a specific OS distribution, as it is the case of the pre-configured images.

The availability of the Ansible role for each supported application is taken for granted within the workflow, since the pre-configured images are also created from them. Having a single, unified approach to describe the application installation and configuration steps, promotes reusability and simplifies maintenance.

The TOSCA document is obtained out of a TOSCA template, explicitly created for each particular application, filled with some runtime parameters. These parameters are provided, as shown in Figure 5, through the interaction with a high-level graphical user interface (GUI) (step 1). The GUI first asks for the user credentials by means of an identity access management service (step 2), then prompts for the selection of the TOSCA template (step 3). For the sake of example, we assume that the user wants to deploy an elastic Mesos cluster.

The INDIGO-DataCloud orchestrator is the entry point to the PaaS layer, receiving TOSCA documents as input (step 4), to find the best match for the resource provisioning. The decision-making process is based on a SLA (Service Level Agreement) analysis and the assessment of the potential target providers availability (step 5), leveraging the INDIGO-DataCloud PaaS service stack [cite INDIGO].

The CMP type of the selected cloud resource provider marks the remaining steps in the TOSCA orchestration workflow. Whenever an OpenStack cloud provider is selected, the orchestrator performs the interaction with the Heat service, preceded by the TOSCA template translation by means of the *Heat Translator* API. As described in Section 3, *Heat Translator* makes use

Fig. 6 Relation among Ansible Roles, Docker images and TOSCA templates.

of *TOSCA Parser* utility to load the TOSCA template, ending up with a OpenStack’s native HOT description of the stack to be deployed.

On the other hand, if the target cloud provider is based on OpenNebula framework or external public cloud platforms (such as Amazon AWS or Google Cloud), then the Orchestrator delegates on the *IM* [5] to perform the provision and the configuration of the virtual infrastructure (step 6). The *IM* component will act as the unified TOSCA orchestrator, receiving the TOSCA template and acting as the orchestration layer with TOSCA support on top of the CMP.

The last steps in the workflow are related to the concrete example of deploying the elastic Apache Mesos cluster. The orchestration layer -*IM* or OpenStack Heat- performs the automated deployment of Mesos, Chronos and Marathon together with CLUES [2], the elasticity manager of the cluster (step 7). The user is then provided with the endpoints to access Chronos and Marathon, both for the actual job submission and the deployment of long-running services, respectively. Once the user starts deploying services or jobs (step 8), CLUES automatically detects that additional resources are required, contacting the Orchestrator (step 9). It will then restart the provisioning process of step 5, resulting in new nodes dynamically added to the existing Mesos cluster (step 10).

Figure 6 describes the relation among the Ansible roles and Docker images, as described in the TOSCA template⁹. The source code of the user applications are available in GitHub together with the Ansible roles that describe their installation and configuration process. Profiting from the GitHub and DockerHub tight integration, automated builds of each application image are triggered once a new change is committed to its repository’s default branch, thus making the last version of the application online available in DockerHub registry. The Ansible roles are also centrally registered in the Ansible Galaxy

⁹ Several examples of TOSCA templates are available in: <https://github.com/indigo-dc/tosca-templates>

online catalog. These Ansible roles are then referenced in the corresponding TOSCA types and used in the TOSCA templates so that applications can be automatically deployed on the provisioned virtual infrastructure.

4 Use Cases

This section illustrates two different use cases that have been implemented within the INDIGO-DataCloud project: A single node based application (Powerfit) and an elastic Mesos cluster.

4.1 Single node: *Powerfit*

In this first case an example of a single-node application is shown. In particular the Powerfit application [19] is used. The reduced version of the TOSCA template required to deploy the application is shown in Listing 3 (the full example is available at *tosca-types* GitHub repository)¹⁰.

In this case the user selects a node type `tosca.nodes.indigo.Powerfit` that has been defined as show in Listing 4. The definition specified the Ansible role needed to install and configure the application. The same Ansible role that is used to build Dhe docker image that is specified in the TOSCA template (`indigodatacloudapps/powerfit`). The deployment of this application follows the steps shown in section 3 using the pre-installed Docker image, on a cloud site that this image is available, or using a vanilla VM or Docker container (in this case based on Ubuntu 14.04).

¹⁰ <https://github.com/indigo-dc/tosca-types/blob/master/examples/powerfit.yaml>

Listing 3 A modified excerpt of the Powerfit TOSCA template.

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0

imports:
  - indigo_types: indigo-dc/tosca-types/master/custom_types.yaml

topology_template:

  node_templates:

    powerfit:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.Powerfit
      requirements:
        - host: p_server

    p_server:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.Compute
      capabilities:
        ...
      os:
        properties:
          type: linux
          distribution: ubuntu
          version: 14.04
          image: indigodatacloudapps/powerfit

    ...
```

Listing 4 `tosca.nodes.indigo.Powerfit` node type definition.

```
tosca.nodes.indigo.HaddockApp:
derived_from: tosca.nodes.SoftwareComponent
properties:
  haddock_app_name:
    type: string
    description: Haddocking application
    required: true
    constraints:
      - valid_values: [ disvis, powerfit ]
artifacts:
  galaxy_role:
    file: indigo-dc.disvis-powerfit
    type: tosca.artifacts.AnsibleGalaxy.role
interfaces:
  Standard:
    configure:
      implementation: https://raw.githubusercontent.com/indigo-dc/
        tosca-types/master/artifacts/haddock/haddock_install.yml
      inputs:
        haddock_app_name: {get_property:[SELF,haddock_app_name]}

tosca.nodes.indigo.Powerfit:
derived_from: tosca.nodes.indigo.HaddockApp
properties:
  haddock_app_name:
    type: string
    required: true
    default: powerfit
    constraints:
      - equal: powerfit
```

This example demonstrates the capability to extend TOSCA with additional non-normative types that best match the application requirements. These new types also link to the specific application deployment procedures that have been properly tested to guarantee the successful deployment of the application under different environments. Having specific types for different applications results in simplified TOSCA templates which enhance readability and, at the same time, prevents users from introducing changes in the deployment procedures of the applications, thus guaranteeing deterministic deployments.

4.2 Elastic Mesos Cluster

Mesos clusters are a widely-known computing facility and virtual mesos clusters in the Cloud enable scientific communities to access customized cluster-based computing on-demand. INDIGO-DataCloud supports the deployment of different type of customized virtual elastic computing clusters defined in TOSCA templates provisioned on the available Cloud infrastructure.

These clusters are elastic since, initially, only the front-end nodes are deployed. Traditional computing clusters, i.e. based on Local Resource Manage-

ment Systems (LRMS) such as SGE, Torque or HTCondor, typically feature a single front-end node. However, Mesos clusters can include a set of master nodes and load balancers. The Mesos masters are customized with the required scientific applications, depending on the target user community. They are also configured with support for CLUES [2], an elasticity management system for clusters that supports several LRMS (e.g. SLURM, PBS/Torque, Mesos). CLUES monitors the state of the job queue to detect when additional Mesos slaves are required to be deployed in order to cope with the number of pending jobs. This way, the cluster can dynamically grow and shrink in terms of the number of slave nodes to adapt to the workload with a limit of maximum number slaves specified in the TOSCA document as "*max_instances*". In INDIGO-DataCloud, CLUES was adapted to provision additional nodes from the PaaS Orchestrator, as well as to introduce elasticity for Apache Mesos Clusters and HTCondor batch resources.

An example of a TOSCA-based description of these virtual elastic computing clusters is available in the *tosca-types* GitHub repository¹¹, summarized in Listing 5. The TOSCA template provides a description of the elastic cluster in terms of the computing requirements for all the Mesos cluster nodes (master, load balancer and slave nodes). It also specifies the maximum number of slaves to launch (5). For the sake of brevity, some information has been omitted in the TOSCA template depicted.

¹¹ http://github.com/indigo-dc/tosca-types/blob/master/examples/mesos_elastic_cluster.yaml

Listing 5 A modified excerpt of the virtual elastic Mesos cluster TOSCA template.

```
tosca_definitions_version: tosca_simple_yaml_1_0

imports:
  - indigo_types: indigo-dc/tosca-types/master/custom_types.yaml

topology_template:

  node_templates:

    elastic_cluster_front_end:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.ElasticCluster
      requirements:
        - lrms: mesos_master
        - wn: mesos_slave

    mesos_master:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.LRMS.FrontEnd.Mesos
      properties:
        marathon_password: marathon_password
        chronos_password: chronos_password
      requirements:
        - host: master_server

    mesos_slave:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.LRMS.WorkerNode.Mesos
      capabilities:
        wn:
          properties:
            max_instances: 5
            min_instances: 0
      properties:
        master_ips: {get_attribute:[master_server,public_address]}
      requirements:
        - host: mesos_slave_server

    mesos_load_balancer:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.MesosLoadBalancer
      properties:
        master_ips: {get_attribute:[master_server,public_address]}
      requirements:
        - host: lb_server

    master_server:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.Compute
      capabilities:
        endpoint:
          properties:
            dns_name: mesosserverpublic
            network_name: PUBLIC
      scalable:
        properties:
          count: 1

    mesos_slave_server:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.Compute

    lb_server:
      type: tosca.nodes.indigo.Compute
      capabilities:
        endpoint:
          properties:
            network_name: PUBLIC
      scalable:
        properties:
          count: 1

  outputs:
    mesos_lb_ips:
      value: { get_attribute: [ lb_server, public_address ] }
    mesos_master_ips:
      value: { get_attribute: [ master_server, public_address ] }
```

It can be seen that TOSCA provides a language to provide a high-level declaration of complex application architectures. However, several non-normative node types were introduced in the context of INDIGO-DataCloud to support both different user applications and specific services to be used within the deployed applications. Indeed, the extensibility of the language and the ability of the underlying TOSCA parser to process these new elements facilitates the procedure of adopting TOSCA as the definition language to perform the orchestration of complex infrastructures across multiple Clouds.

5 Conclusions

This paper has described the challenges of orchestrating in heterogeneous clouds and the approach carried out in the INDIGO-DataCloud project to overcome it. The TOSCA standard has been adopted for the description of application architectures to be deployed on a Cloud, focusing on the definition of complex computing application architectures.

Different examples have been shown that range from a simple single-node application to an elastic Apache Mesos cluster to execution batch jobs and long-running services via the Chronos and the Marathon framework. For this, an orchestration approach based on prioritizing cloud sites with existing pre-configured Docker images is employed, while being able to dynamically deploy the applications on cloud sites supporting only vanilla VMs or Docker images. By adopting Ansible Roles as both the deployment artifacts of the TOSCA templates and the procedure to create Docker images, a single consistent unified approach for application delivery is employed.

Future work includes supporting different complex application architectures used by scientific communities. Examples of this include architectures for Big Data processing in order to automatically provision virtual computing clusters to process large volumes of data using existing frameworks such as Hadoop and Spark). Also, the ability to perform hybrid deployments across multiple cloud sites specified in the TOSCA template as part of the requirements of the applications.

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